

Connect Data Workflows & Create Machine Actionable DMP Templates

FACTSHEET FOR ARGOS ADMINISTRATORS

Argos Administrator

- ▶ Create machine actionable templates and dataset profiles
- ▶ Combine many types of input (e.g. multiple choice, free text, boolean) to form one question
- ▶ Define the flow of the questions and their dependencies
- ▶ Connect with internal and external authoritative sources (APIs) and services (e.g. data repository, researchers registries)

Argos users can become admins upon request: argos@openaire.eu

DMP in Argos

Main Info

DMP Templates provide basic fields to describe administrative information about the DMPs.

Dataset Info

Dataset Templates provide the structure and the questions to describe how Datasets are handled by researchers according to Research Data Management policies and practices.

Build a Dataset Template in 3 simple steps

Give a title, a description and define the language

Build the structure, add dataset questions and define the flow

Check how the template looks like, test it and make it visible to researchers

About **argos**

argos simplifies the creation of machine actionable templates and connects them with data workflows to enhance validated information. Admins can easily add and move around questions and have access to a collection of re-usable APIs. Researchers minimize their effort in writing DMPs that infer information in a standard way.

Update the template at any time (new version)

Share administrative rights and co-develop the template with colleagues

Connect DMPs with local services and Open Science ecosystems

- Use the OpenAIRE and EOSC APIs & configure your own APIs
- Integrate with your local repository to publish DMPs
- Automate the creation of dataset profiles in DMPs & establish direct communication with repository managers
- Enrich the OpenAIRE Research Graph with contextualized information for your DMPs and create links between DMPs, research outputs and semantics
- Send contextualized information of DMPs to your OpenAIRE Monitoring Dashboard, define indicators & exploit DMPs evaluation, uptake and RDM trends
- Integrate with your discovery service & provide visibility to DMPs

Use Argos in OpenAIRE or deploy Argos

	Customize ARGOS Online	Deploy software
Domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Use Argos online instance → Use OpenAIRE domain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Create and name your own instance → Choose own or use OpenAIRE domain
Login	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Authenticate users via OpenAIRE and EOSC AAI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Authenticate users via OpenAIRE and EOSC AAI and / or connect with other, compliant, identity providers
Interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Localize editors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Localize tool → Set own logo → Modify colours, fonts, size of text etc → Overlay support tools.
Publish dmps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Use Zenodo, the OpenAIRE and CERN repository → Link to Zenodo communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Use Zenodo, the OpenAIRE and CERN repository, or configure own repository → Link to repository communities / collections
Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Information inferred from OpenAIRE trusted sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Information inferred from OpenAIRE trusted sources and / or configured own APIs
Statistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Get contextualized Argos DMP data → Add Argos DMP data to your MONITOR Dashboards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Get contextualized Argos DMP data → Add Argos DMP data to own monitoring systems
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Access user base 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Access and manage user base → Control access

Useful Links

Argos Homepage

<https://argos.openaire.eu/home>

Argos User Guide

<https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/resources/user-guide.html>

Check Argos development

<https://trello.com/b/x49lylnK/argos>

Source code

<https://code-repo.d4science.org/Madgik-CITE/argos>

OpenAIRE APIs

<https://develop.openaire.eu/>

Contact us

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